

ENGLISH FOR SONG LOVER: HOW ONE CAN ENHANCE HIS ENGLISH BY SONGS

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Annotation: *The article below is very helpful for learner of English who are obsessed with singing in English*

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There are many methods of learning a foreign language, some of them are more successful, while others are very poor. Quite often, the effectiveness of one method or another lies in clever tricks that make learning a fun process or even a game. Memorization for many is a repeated repetition: but for something to really remain in the baggage of our consciousness for a long time, a good memory is not enough. For the development of memory and the training of diction, children from an early age to the last grades are forced to learn poetry and prose passages. The child memorizes the text for a long time, but after a while he forgets it. But it is noticed that we rarely specially learn the words of popular hits or songs we like, they are remembered by themselves. What's the secret?

A beautiful melody is a very vivid and impressive phenomenon for our consciousness. We like the song, we listen carefully and, if the words turn out to be interesting for us, they are remembered effortlessly through several auditions. We want to listen, remember and sing along.

But the phenomenon of memorizing songs described above applies only to songs in the language that we understand.

The idea of learning English while singing is only good if you know the language a little. If you do not know a single word, English songs will be equated to bird chirping for you: the song of birds is wonderful, but it is completely impossible to find out the meaning of the song.

The second important point arguing why the basic types of learning cannot be neglected is that the human ear is accustomed to distinguishing only those sounds that completely coincide with the sounds of our native speech. Sounds that are not in our native language, our consciousness "adjusts" to the usual. We just don't hear them the way we need to, and pronounce them in our own way. It is for this reason that many Japanese learners of the Russian language speak "halaso" instead of "good." In Japanese, there is no sound that conveys the letter "P", and it is replaced by a more

appropriate one. The same happens when learning English. Therefore, in addition to listening to the song in English, it would be nice to see how its words are written, and it is also advisable to do certain phonetic exercises.

To successfully learn English through songs, you need to have audio recordings of songs, their lyrics in English and its translation. Karaoke can be a great help for your lessons. Learning by listening to songs in English is rewarding and effective, but it must be done correctly.

It is very important to know that not every song is suitable for learning English with it. Many modern American and English songs, especially Rap, are replete with slang words and phrases that can make your speech understandable to guys from not very prosperous American neighborhoods, but completely unsuitable for communicating with the English queen.

To enrich your vocabulary, you need vocabulary for normal everyday communication. Therefore, when choosing English songs for training, it would be ideal to focus on such directions as Jazz, Blues, Folk and Country. Opera and Musical are also suitable here, but these genres have not been at all popular among students lately. And the above four genres may be beyond your musical preferences.

Modern youth more often listen to Pop, R&B, Rap, Alternative, Rock. Here we are in a difficult situation: in order for learning to be effective, you need to listen to exactly what is interesting, but at the same time you need to learn the "correct" language. The solution is simple: you can entrust the selection of materials for individual learning with songs to an experienced teacher who will filter out songs with gross grammatical errors from your favorite playlist, or explain when phrases from songs will be inappropriate during communication.

For training, it is advisable to choose solo versions of songs. Multiple performers and backing vocals can be difficult to understand.

The fact that minimal knowledge is required to learn English by learning songs does not mean at all that you cannot sing from the first lessons. You can and even need to sing. But accept the fact that the songs you will sing are childish.

Even while learning their native language, children sing a lot. Singing in kindergarten is not only the development of a child's ear for music, but also a kind of exercise for the development of diction and articulation, which also trains the memorization of new words in the native language. Therefore, for those who want to sing from the first lessons, children's songs are quite suitable. If this moment confuses you, postpone singing until you can understand at least a few words from your chosen song.

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